

DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF AUTOMATIC WEEDS REMOVAL AND PESTICIDES SPRAYER

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Abstract

Agriculture must undergo significant modernization to effectively meet the evolving demands of an expanding population and the rapidly advancing industrial landscape. The integration of advanced mechanization technologies presents numerous advantages, such as enabling precise metering processes that enhance input conservation, optimize distribution channels, reduce required reaction quantities, and effectively curtail wastage. This mechanization not only serves to streamline operations but also plays a pivotal role in minimizing production overheads by bolstering output levels and ensuring the sustainable management of vital resources. Over the years, agricultural practices have remained largely unchanged, with farmers relying on age-old techniques and outdated equipment that have been passed down through generations. Despite the prevalence of traditional farming methods in our country, there has been a notable surge in growth within the industrial and service sectors. Manual spraying methods using backpack sprayers have dominated the agricultural landscape, demanding considerable physical effort. Similarly, the labor-intensive process of weeding, often carried out with the assistance of bulls, highlights the industry's underlying resistance to embracing more efficient and technologically advanced approaches.

Keywords: smart farming, mechanization, back type sprayer, weeding, modernization, DC motor, Blades, Battery.

I. Introduction

Automatic additional crop removal technology involves advanced machinery that efficiently targets and eliminates unwanted plants within agricultural fields. By utilizing cutting-edge sensors, mobile-controlled devices, and robotics, farmers can precisely identify and remove the surplus crops, promoting more sustainable and productive farming practices. Furthermore, the utilization of automation in pesticide spraying enhances the effectiveness of pest control measures. By deploying state-of-the-art machines to spray insecticides, farmers can combat pests with precision, reducing the environmental impact caused by excessive chemical usage. This innovative approach not only saves valuable time for farmers but also significantly improves overall farming efficiency and sustainability. It optimizes agriculture processes by reducing the reliance on manual labor and streamlining operations through the integration of technology. With the accurate deployment of pesticides and removal of unwanted plants, the farming industry can achieve higher yields while minimizing the negative effects on the environment. In summary, the merging of technology with farming practices through the implementation of automated crop removal and pesticide spraying methods aims to revolutionize traditional agriculture. Through the precise application of resources and the reduction of pesticides, this technological advancement plays a key role in promoting sustainable and efficient farming techniques for the future.

Figure 1: Progression of cutting weeds

The primary objective of this crucial project is to effectively address the pressing demand for sustainable and efficient methods of weed control and pesticide application within agricultural fields. It is widely recognized that the current practices of manual weeding and indiscriminate pesticide spraying not only impose significant labor burdens and consume excessive time but also pose adverse consequences on the environment. In light of these challenges, the project aims to introduce a transformative solution: an innovative automatic system designed for weed removal and pesticide spraying. This cutting-edge system will leverage state-of-the-art technology, including advanced sensors, sophisticated computer vision capabilities, and precision robotics to identify and eliminate weeds while accurately administering pesticides only where necessary. By seamlessly integrating weed detection and pesticide application into a single coherent automated process, the system is poised to revolutionize agricultural activities, leading to operational efficiencies, substantial reductions in labor expenses, and a marked decrease in pesticide usage. Such a comprehensive approach not only addresses the immediate challenges faced by farmers but also heralds a new era of sustainable farming practices. Precision Agriculture

II. Related work

Intelligent information appliances, which rely on advanced technology to optimize irrigation field appliance control, represent the cutting-edge direction of development in the field. In line with this trend, we have meticulously designed and produced a varied and impressive assortment of Super Mini Electric Weed Cutters equipped with integrated pesticide sprayers. These innovative tools not only streamline the process of weed management in agricultural settings but also underscore our commitment to providing farmers with efficient and sustainable solutions. By harnessing the power of automation and data-driven decision-making, our products empower users to enhance crop yield while minimizing resource wastage. The Super Mini Electric Weed Cutters stand out as a testament to our dedication to merging technology and agriculture seamlessly. Through continuous research and

development, we strive to remain at the forefront of industry innovation, catering to the evolving needs of modern farming practice

Advantages

Reduced amount of insecticide used by 50%

- Higher velocities during the spraying procedure
- Less complex movements
- More efficient
- Reduces losses
- Increases precision
- Ability to reach high precision
- Ability to reduce losses
- Ability to be more efficient

Fig:2

Working model of automated weeds removal and pesticides sprayer assembling all the components

III. Proposed methodology

A portable electric weed cutting machine with pesticide sprayer is employed. To achieve the goals of the proposed idea, we must first learn the fundamentals of a few electronics components such as the ESP32, 1298, rechargeable battery, geared DC motor, cutting blades, and so on.

a. ESP32

ESP32 consists of dual core processors which run at frequencies up to 240 MHz It uses Extensa single/dual-core 32-bit LX6 microprocessor. It houses 448 KB ROM, 520 KB SRAM, 16 KB SRAM in RTC and supports multiple flash/SRAM chips using QSPI interface. It has analog/digital input and output pins, clocks, timers and multiple communication interfaces such as GPIOs, UART, SPI, I2C, I2S etc. It houses Wi-Fi (802.11b/g/n), Bluetooth v4.2 and BLE functionalities which enables wireless communication with other devices.

Fig:3 Image of ESP32

b. Rechargeable Battery:

The lead acid battery is a type of rechargeable battery first invented in 1859 by French physicist Gaston Planté. It is the first type of rechargeable battery ever created. Compared to modern rechargeable batteries, lead–acid batteries have relatively low energy density. Despite this, their ability to supply high surge currents means that the cells have a relatively large power-to-weight ratio. These features, along with their low cost, make them attractive for use in motor vehicles to provide the high current required by starter motors.

Fig:4 Rechargeable Battery

c. DC motor

A DC motor is any of a class of rotary electrical motors that converts direct current electrical energy into mechanical energy. The most common types rely on the forces produced by magnetic fields. Nearly all types of DC motors have some internal mechanism, either electromechanical or electronic; to periodically change the direction of current in part of the motor. Where in this system totally six geared DC motor is used and fixed in hexagonal frame. DC motors were the first form of motor widely used, as they could be powered from existing direct current lighting power distribution systems. A DC motor's speed can be controlled over a wide range, using either a variable supply voltage or by changing the strength of current in its field windings. Small DC motors are used in tools, toys, and appliances. The universal motor can operate on direct current but is a lightweight brushed motor used for portable power tools and appliances. Larger DC motors are currently used in propulsion of electric vehicles, elevator and hoists, and in drives for steel rolling mills. The advent of power electronics has made replacement of DC motors with AC motors possible in many applications.

Voltage rating: 12V

Amp rating: 2A

Torque: 10 kg.cm

Speed: 30rpm

Fig:5 DC motor

d. Cutter Motor

Fig:6 Cutter motor

DC 12V 24V round shaft 775 electric motors, with both side bush, Mounting Screw Hole Diameter: 4mm, Distance between Screw Holes: 30mm, Diameter of the Motor: 44mm.
 Type: Micro DC Motor; Rated voltage: 12V 2 Amp, No Load Speed: 6000RPM, 12V 5Amp Shaft Diameter: 5 mm; Shaft length: 17 mm Length of the Motor (Body): 67mm, Motor Diameter: 45mm, Color: Silver Tone. With metal material torque DC motor, lightweight, resistant abrasion and tough features, durable and reliable even you use it for long time the motor starting current needs to be 10A, Net Weight: 315gm,

e. Water pump

This DC 12V Mini Submersible Noiseless Water Pump is a low cost, small size Submersible Pump Motor which can be operated from a 12V power supply. It can take up to 120 liters per hour with a very low current consumption of 220mA. Just connect the tube pipe to the motor outlet, submerge it in water, and power it.

Make sure that the water level is always higher than the motor. The dry run may damage the motor due to heating and it will also produce noise.

Battery Sprayer Pump 12V 5A Flow Rate: 80 to 120 L/H Type: single diaphragm
 Input and Output pipe size:4.5 and 7.35 mm

Fig:7 Water pump

IV. Calculation

Force Calculation

Assuming weight of the machine,

$$W = 5.5 \text{ kg} \quad W = 5.5 \times 9.81 \quad W = 53.955 \text{ N}$$

DC Geared motor: Per Motor

Rated Current: Rated Current (A) = Rated Power (W) / Operating Voltage (VDC) =
 $9.6 \text{ W} / 12\text{V} = 0.8 \text{ A}$

Mechanical Output Power: Mechanical Output Power (W) = Rated Torque (kg-cm) *
 Rated Speed (RPM) * $2 * \pi / 60 = 8 \text{ kg-cm} * 24 \text{ RPM} * 2 * \pi / 60 \approx 4.17 \text{ W}$

First, let us convert the rated torque from kg-cm to N-cm

$$8 \text{ kg-cm} = 8 \times 9.8 \text{ N-cm/kg-cm} = 78.4 \text{ N-cm.}$$

Now, we calculate the torque at the output shaft of the gearbox:

Output Torque = Rated Torque x Gear Ratio

$$\text{Output Torque} = 78.4 \text{ N-cm} \times 150$$

$$\text{Torque} = 11760 \text{ N-cm}$$

Battery Consumption Calculation:

Battery Capacity = 9Ah

Voltage = 12V

Motor Power = 9.6W

(per motor)

$$\begin{aligned} @ 4 \text{ DC gear Motors} &= 9.6 \times 4 \\ &= 38.4 \text{ W} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{9 \times 12\text{v}}{9.6} = 11.25 \text{ hrs}$$

$$\begin{aligned} @ 3 \text{ DC Trimmer motors} &= 19.7 \times 2 \\ &= 39.2 \text{ W} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{9 \times 12\text{v}}{77.6} = 1.4 \text{ hrs}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total Running time} &= 1.40 \text{ hrs.} = 84 \text{ mins} \\ &= 1.40 \text{ Hours} \\ &= 84 \text{ mins} \end{aligned}$$

V. Result

The design and fabrication of an automatic weeds removal and pesticides sprayer system involves a meticulous process to create an efficient and reliable solution for agricultural needs. Beginning with a thorough analysis of requirements, including targeted weed types, field dimensions, crop varieties, and environmental factors, the design phase conceptualizes various approaches to meet these needs. Mechanical design focuses on crafting durable and efficient components for weed removal and pesticide spraying, while electrical and electronic design encompasses sensors, actuators, and control systems to detect weeds and manage system operation. Software development plays a crucial role in creating algorithms and user interfaces to control weed detection and pesticide application. Prototyping brings these elements together, integrating mechanical, electrical, and software components for testing and evaluation in real- world conditions. Feedback from testing informs refinement and optimization efforts, aiming to enhance performance, efficiency, and reliability. Finally, production and deployment processes are undertaken, ensuring mass production readiness and seamless integration into agricultural settings, with ongoing maintenance and support provided to sustain long-term effectiveness and minimize negative impacts

VI. Conclusion

The equipment is purposely design for the farmers having small farming land say 5-6 acre. It is suitable for spraying as well as weeding at minimum cost for the farmer so that he can afford it. The equipment will result more beneficial when it is subjected to moist soil for weeding purpose, due to moist soil the weed cutter can easily penetrate and dig out the soil and hence will easily accomplished the weeding process.

VII. REFERENCE

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